

Developing the Fundamental Research in Finance, Credit and Banking in the Context of an Innovative Economy

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Abstract: *The article more consistently identifies the factors influencing the development of fundamental research in the field of finance, credit and banks, which is a serious obstacle to the practical implementation of the investment idea. It is noted that the limitations of our knowledge in the field of financial and banking systems significantly slows down the dynamic development of the economy, slowing down the innovation process. The weakening of theoretical research, applied research can also lead to the loss of their innovative character. In this regard, the article provides specific proposals that can implement the goals of innovative development. It is noted that with an innovative approach to development, it is necessary to take into account the feasibility of increasing the state's efforts to increase revenues from non-tax revenues, the share of which should reach approximately 3-4% of GDP.*

The article also notes that the lack of clear standards for banking activities not only prevents the implementation of the goals of innovative development, but also significantly hinders the use of the most effective examples of organization and management in the country's banking sector. Therefore, the article notes that it is necessary to set fundamentally new tasks for control bodies, and for this purpose it is necessary to quickly improve the regulatory framework for financial control.

Key words: *lending, inflation, innovative project, renewal of fixed capital, sources of credit resources, bank deposits, money supply, refinancing rate, foreign exchange reserves, fundamental research of knowledge, single organism, financial system, banking standards, performance assessment, crisis situations, innovative project, strategic audit, financial control.*

In fairness, it should be noted that the current lack of comprehensive research, in particular fundamental research in the field of finance, taxes, credit and banks, is a serious obstacle to the practical implementation of innovative ideas.

Behind the mass of proposals and recommendations concerning the innovative path of economic development, there is actually a lack of understanding of what innovations in the financial and banking spheres of activity should consist of. The limitations of scientific approaches and knowledge in the field of financial and banking systems can significantly slow down the dynamic development of the economy, accordingly, slowing down the innovation process, and, thus, lead to the loss of the essence of the innovative nature of economic development.

In the conditions of innovative development of the economy, when assessing the role of the financial and banking sectors, it is necessary to proceed from the fact that each of them represents a certain whole, whether the set of their elements has been fully formed and whether the interaction between the elements has been established. The financial and banking systems are not a single organism that can claim to have completed the formation of modern financial science. In the financial system, there is a noticeable

weakness in the interaction between republican and territorial finances. The financial infrastructure is also not established at the proper level. In the banking system, there is no more modern banking structure that can support innovatively developing enterprises; changes are often made to the banking legislation.

Consequently, the reason for this phenomenon is seen in the absence of clear standards within the framework of banking activities, which not only affects the implementation of the goal of innovative development, but also significantly hinders the use of the most effective patterns of organization and management in the banking sector of the country. However, the source of this problem is standards, that is, standards of banking activities, as some of its patterns, reflecting international and domestic experience, the best banking practice, relate not only to the quality of banking activities (which is very important from an economic point of view), but also to such its most important characteristics as the purpose of banking activities, its principles and results. The system of indicators reflecting international experience in assessing the effectiveness of banking activities does not yet exist. Therefore, conducting a review of domestic and foreign experience is extremely important. However, it is impossible (or unacceptable) to blindly copy the experience of foreign countries. Although, experts have been looking for a solution to it for many years, blindly using the experience of foreign countries. That is why this problem is relevant both for our Republic and for many countries of the post-Soviet space.

The need to develop a system of indicators reflecting, among other things, negative crisis phenomena is especially urgent. Crisis detection, development of a system of indicators - harbingers of crisis situations - is an essential task of banking science and practice. Here, however, it is important to distinguish between signs of weakness of the banking system, impulses that provoke bankruptcy of banks, symptoms of an approaching crisis, signs of a pre-crisis (critical) state of the banking system, the onset of a crisis.

It is worth noting that an innovative approach to economic development should be considered the interaction of both the financial and banking systems. This approach to assessing interaction, although correct, has not been sufficiently studied. It is important to combine them with each other, as well as between them and the strategic policy of the state.

The insignificant share of the current investment in the innovation sector of the economy (0.3% of the corresponding US figure) and the need for significant growth in innovation investment indicate that scientific thought, actually embodied in a specific result, and successful scientific activity in our country are not yet a criterion of social efficiency, an indicator of social success. In this situation, one cannot expect that all potential forces will be thrown into innovation activity in the near future and the situation with the search for effective innovation projects will improve dramatically.

In our opinion, it is necessary to set fundamentally new tasks for financial authorities, and for this purpose it is necessary to quickly improve the regulatory framework for financial control and the control bodies implementing it. Based on the current work of the Accounts Chamber of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the implementation of performance audit, it is entirely possible to consider the development of a new direction for the implementation of state financial control - strategic audit, designed to control the resource provision of innovative development of the economy, including control over the validity of the allocation of budget funds and the effectiveness of their use, as timely.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, in order to strengthen financial control, it is necessary to develop a new regulation on conducting a strategic audit, and this should be reflected in legislation, including in regulations governing the implementation of financial control over the activities of state corporations responsible for innovative development. Currently, this type of control is interpreted much more broadly. However, this is impossible as long as there are discussions regarding the very concept of "innovation". Our research has shown that there is no clear idea of the system of control over the ineffective use of instruments for regulating the development of fundamental research in the field of

finance, credit and banks that is necessary for the Republic of Uzbekistan. Therefore, without a clearly defined term, regulatory authorities will actually be deprived of the opportunity to effectively control the innovative activities of economic entities.

Touching upon the issue of venture capital, it can be noted that the results of the activities of venture companies, gradually occupying their niche in the market, cannot be called successful: according to the results of work in 2020 - a loss of 7 billion soums. Large companies, except for Naftogaz, are somewhat distrustful of the proposed public-private partnership, as evidenced by the lack of applications for participation in the first competitive selection of management companies. Most of the declared companies are not professional participants in the venture capital market and manage pension money, which is usually not invested in high-risk projects. The regulatory framework for the work of management companies has not been fully formed, which calls into question the effectiveness of this form of public-private partnership.

It should be noted that the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Economic Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan do not pay enough attention to the introduction of new financial institutions and financial products.

In conclusion, it can be said that the systematic implementation of the above approaches, in particular, and the study of the advantages of the experience of implementing innovations without taking into account domestic specifics in practice will play an important role in increasing the effectiveness of joint financial management of innovations.

Although, in terms of approach to providing financial and banking services, Uzbekistan does not build its own unique model, but adopts international experience that has been tested for decades. But it should be noted that the Republic also has some peculiarities in managing innovations.

Hence the conclusion that foreign experience should acquaint us with the most advanced knowledge in the sphere of financial and banking services. All this should encourage the governing bodies to implement the proven long-term breakthrough experience of other industrially developed countries.

In Uzbekistan, the experience of implementing innovations accumulated in the financial market of the USA or Russia is often used predominantly, without taking into account domestic specifics, which distinguishes our practice from Germany, where a huge amount of work has been done to carefully select the best financial innovations formed in the Anglo-Saxon markets.

Over the past 10 years, no system of institutional investors has been created in Uzbekistan: the funds of insurance companies and non-state pension funds are insignificant. In this regard, the Association of Banks should develop a project to develop the availability of financial services for the population.

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